

A PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR PROMOTING ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AMONG REFUGEES IN JORDAN

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Abstract

In Jordan, thousands of refugees seek a job as their first option to finance themselves and their families instead of being self-employed or establishing their businesses. This paper proposes a conceptual framework for further exploration and examination of the entrepreneurial intention among refugees in Jordan. The framework suggests that entrepreneurial education, social marketing, and public policies can promote entrepreneurial intentions among refugees.

Keywords: Employment, Entrepreneurship, Self-Employment, Promotion, Entrepreneurial Awareness, Promoting Entrepreneurship.

UNEMPLOYMENT AND REFUGEE CRISIS

The rise of unemployment in specific youth and the troubling economic growth has attracted the attention of economists, policymakers, and academic researchers towards advancing and progressing in setting policies and strategies that will promote the entrepreneurial spirit and expedite wealth creation (Zahra, 2011). Thus, the identification of the motivation for entrepreneurial deeds is more and more being recognized (Renko et al., 2015). Entrepreneurial behavior is precipitated by intentions to conduct such behavior (Vamvaka et al., 2020). Human intentions are a good predictor of entrepreneurial behavior (Ndofirepi et al., 2017). However, there has yet to be a consensus on the theoretical explanations for entrepreneurial intentions (López-Delgado et al., 2019). Further, it is argued that “entrepreneurship is a process that can be applied to the creation of economic or social ends” (Cukier et al., 2011, p. 100).

From the international donors’ perception, ensuring that refugees have legal access to the labor market in the host countries is mandatory, like Jordan, to ensure that refugees stay in the origin region. On the host country level, the problem emerges as a source of a quandary; since refugee employment is a severe problem for refugees’ “self-reliance and local integration” On the contrary, it is identified as the source of competition for already scarce job opportunities for host countries like Jordan. From a refugee perspective, having access to the labor market and getting support are ways of gaining sustainable livelihood opportunities, self-reliance, and dignity (Mencuttek, & Nashwan, 2021) In this regard, to face any social problem, according to Rothchild (1999), education, regulations, and marketing are vital for avoiding social issues; in his context, it was public health. Conversely, in the context of this paper, the researcher is

concentrating on the refugee unemployment problem. Moreover, to promote entrepreneurial intention among refugees through a proposed framework. The framework is based on three main paradigms: entrepreneurial education, social marketing, and regulations (policies that ease obstacles that entrepreneurs face in specific refugees in Jordan, which will play a vital role in lowering the unemployment among refugees)

ENTREPRENEURSHIP INTENTION

The importance of entrepreneurship in developing the national economy is well-recognized internationally by policymakers, economists, and academic researchers. However, entrepreneurship has been advanced as the solution for unemployment, in specific youth. Further, it can offer refugees a stable income, independence, and self-sufficiency; whether the creation of intention toward it is worth exploring entrepreneurship intentions needed to be more visible and evident (Ojiaku et al., 2018; Nowiński & Haddoud, 2019). Further, there are arguments in previous entrepreneurial studies about whether researching it is worth exploring (Nowiński & Haddoud). Factually, intentions have been defined as “self-prediction to engage in a behavior” (Bae et al., 2014, p. 219). Social-psychosomatic studies presume that intention is a distinct predictor of actual entrepreneurial behavior. Nevertheless, there is doubt about whether intentions predict actual entrepreneurial behavior (Doanh et al., 2021). Nonetheless, multiple studies still regard entrepreneurial intentions as one of the crucial antecedents of actual entrepreneurial actions (Lu et al., 2021).

The main concern is that intention may not transfer into actual entrepreneurial behavior. Because entrepreneurial purpose, for example, opening a small business decision and actual behavior, does not happen immediately, being an entrepreneur is a choice. Firstly, the person intends to start a business before fulfilling the behavior (Liñán, 2004). The appropriateness of entrepreneurial intention depends on the research question. The entrepreneurial intention should be an appropriate outcome for studies on nascent entrepreneurs whose intentions might only lead to start-up behaviors several years later. For example, individuals who intend to start a capital-intensive business cannot do so immediately because of resource scarcity (Hsu et al., 2019).

ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION

Entrepreneurial education is spreading extensively over the past three decades; courses have been implemented in universities and schools on different educational levels, and universities are spending a tremendous amount of money on developing entrepreneurship courses (Liñán, 2004; Turker & Selcuk, 2009). Apart from the traditional educational institutions, programs are carried out for specific audiences, mainly for different subgroups such as unemployed people, minorities, and refugees (Liñán, 2004). Therefore, entrepreneurial education can influence the development of entrepreneurial intentions, attitudes, abilities, and skills among youth. Moreover, entrepreneurial education may positively affect entrepreneurial intentions, predominantly in how it chemistries with self-efficacy and personal beliefs (Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2015). Moreover, it can develop innovative talents, a valuable skill for entrepreneurs

(Wei et al., 2019).

SOCIAL MARKETING

Many social problems were tackled by applying modern marketing concepts. Implicit or exact utilization of marketing principles for avoiding or decreasing social; problems such as drug consumption, smoking, violence, Etc. (Mukattash et al., 2021; Wallace-Williams et al., 2022), which coined the term “social marketing” in the seventies of the last century (Singh et al., 2015). Unemployment is a severe social problem that can be tackled by promoting the self-employment mentality among citizens through entrepreneurship, freelance work, or opening a small business (Eppler-Hattab, 2021) Entrepreneurs deciding to be an entrepreneur is challenging, as many entrepreneurs, specifically females, can face several challenges arising from the socio-cultural, economical, lawful, political, and technological surroundings of developing economies countries (Amine & Staub, 2009; Madill & Ziegler, 2012).

PROPOSED CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework contains theories, concepts, and empirical findings from previous literature. Moreover, it indicates relationships among these ideas and how they relate to the research study (Imenda, 2014). The following diagram illustrates the proposed framework, which represents motivational factors that can encourage entrepreneurial intention among refugees, which assumes that policymakers, with a partnership with international donors, should ease the barriers for refugees, besides entrepreneurial education through training programs at not-for-profit centers at the host countries, besides social marketing campaigns that promote and raises the awareness for the importance of self-employment, especially in countries where jobs are scarce for the citizens not only refugees.

FINDINGS, LIMITATIONS, AND FURTHER EXPLORATION

The research suggests that promotion, easing regulations, and entrepreneurial education are vital for fighting employment among refugees, as refugee crises such as the Syrian refugee crisis expose challenges for refugees and the host countries, like Jordan, where jobs are scarce for its citizens. Thus, it exposes the country economically and socially to problems, so this study offers the model for further inductive exploration, as this study was limited as there was no data collection. The model can be helpful for policymakers, economists, and academic researchers.

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